

Rice-based cropping systems

Groundnut varieties for summer rice fallows

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In 1980 we evaluated 93 groundnut varieties for cultivation in summer rice fallows at the Mannuthy Agricultural Research Station. All the varieties established satisfactorily, and 31 were selected for further evaluation in comparative yield trials (Table 1).

Duration to maturity ranged from 95 d for Exotic 6 to 117 d for M-13. ICG3859 had the highest fresh haulms yield, 20 t/ha; followed by S-7-5-13, 17 t/ha; and AH6915, 17 t/ha. TG3 ranked first in pod yield with 3.2 t/ha. The recommended varieties TMV2 and TMV7 yielded only 2 t/ha. None of the promising varieties were damaged by pests.

Based on yield and other desirable characters, six varieties and two check varieties were chosen for multilocation testing in farmer fields at five sites. Tests were in a randomized block design with three replications.

In pod yield TG3 was best, followed by TG14 and Spanish Improved (Table 2). TG3 and TG14 are bunch varieties evolved at the Biology and Agriculture Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay. TG3 is an x-ray induced mutant and TG14 is a derivative of a cross between two mutants from the same Spanish Improved. The two varieties have been approved by the Variety Evaluation Committee of Kerala Agricultural University for large-scale cultivation. □

Table 1. Pod yield and other important characters of 31 selected groundnut varieties, Kerala, India.

Variety	Duration (d)	Fresh haulms yield (t/ha)	Dry pod yield (t/ha)	100-pd wt (g)	Shelling (%)	Oil content (%)	Protein content (%)
EC21118	101	15.4	2.3	82	78	46	25
ICG3859	105	20.5	2.6	110	67	49	25
EC36892	111	14.2	2.9	142	70	43	29
S-7-5-13	112	16.9	2.5	103	61	54	26
EC112027	96	13.3	2.9	90	78	47	23
B353	106	9.0	1.9	83	76	49	26
EC35999	99	13.7	2.9	101	75	47	26
EC119704	112	12.2	2.6	113	69	47	28
AH6915	113	16.6	2.5	140	67	53	27
M-13	117	13.4	2.4	107	69	42	30
Spanish Improved	99	14.3	3.1	91	73	48	26
Dh-3-30	98	14.4	2.7	87	73	49	25
Jyothi	98	13.1	2.6	103	76	50	26
Exotic 6	95	16.2	2.6	78	78	48	27
TMV9	100	9.4	2.9	88	75	47	26
TMV10	106	14.8	2.6	88	71	52	23
AK-811	102	14.3	2.7	86	78	48	27
TMV2	107	9.1	2.4	108	75	47	25
KG6 1-240	99	12.5	2.6	71	81	47	25
TMVII	109	9.3	2.5	125	72	43	25
Pollachi-2	97	15.1	3.1	83	78	46	25
TG3	99	14.9	3.2	99	73	47	24
TG14	106	11.3	3.1	102	71	47	26
TG17	101	11.3	2.5	121	71	49	29
TG19	98	12.8	2.7	92	73	48	26
Pollachi 1	100	11.5	2.9	113	69	45	25
TMV7	98	14.1	1.8	84	77	48	25
Gangapuri	98	16.3	1.5	92	69	49	26
Big Japan	110	11.7	2.5	98	57	48	28
Co 1	106	7.8	2.7	90	76	50	26
JL 24	99	7.4	2.5	108	74	48	28
CD (0.05)	2.7	2.91	0.434	1.4	1.1	0.7	1.1

Table 2. Dry pod yield of selected groundnut varieties in multilocation trials at 5 sites, Kerala, India.

Variety	Dry pod yield (t/ha)					Mean
	Mannuthy	Puthur	Kodassery	Puthukod	Malampuzha	
TG14	2.42	2.26	2.50	2.23	2.95	2.47
Spanish Improved	2.17	2.37	2.37	2.39	2.33	2.33
TG3	2.56	2.61	2.97	2.51	3.07	2.75
Pollachi 2	2.43	2.26	2.31	2.26	2.43	2.34
EC35999	2.41	2.25	2.38	2.29	2.27	2.32
TMV2	1.91	2.08	2.19	1.93	2.35	2.09
TMV7	1.98	1.88	2.50	1.85	2.07	2.05
JL 24	2.19					2.19
CD (0.05)	0.111	0.225	0.258	0.143	0.242	0.267

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